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THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF INNOVATIVE AND ENTREPRENEURIAL TEACHERS IN APPLICATION-ORIENTED UNIVERSITIES: BASIS FOR AN ACTION PLAN

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the professional competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in application-oriented universities. It aimed to assess the development status of teachers' professional competence. There are six(6) dimensions of teachers' professional competence, including teaching, scientific research and professional development, entrepreneurship training and guidance, communication and cooperation, student education and management, and resource integration. The participants of the study are 160 innovative and entrepreneurial teachers from 10 application-oriented universities in Guangxi, China.

The findings showed that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers' professional competence in six(6) dimensions presented unbalanced development. They showed a high level in four(4) dimensions: students' education and management, communication and cooperation, teaching and resource integration. However, scientific research and professional development, entrepreneurship training and guidance showed moderate level.

Based on the above conclusions, this study put forward the action plan for innovative and entrepreneurial teachers. The results of the study can be used as an important basis for improving the professional competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in application-oriented universities, and as a useful reference for educational administrators to carry out practice and formulate policies.

Keywords: Professional Competence, Innovative and Entrepreneurial Teachers, Application-Oriented Universities, Action Plan

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Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right, and it also serves as the motive power for the sustainable development of society. It has cultivated an exceptional array of scientific and technological talents for the society, facilitated the widespread application of science and technology in social production, thereby igniting round after round of industry revolutions. Globally, these new scientific and technological revolutions have fostered an unceasing surge of new production methods, organizational structures, and business models. Indeed, the new scientific and technological revolution promoted profound changes in the field of education itself as well as promoting changes in industrial orientation, business model and social ecology. Digital technology propelled the innovation of innovative learning methods, teaching models, and management strategies. Information technology acted on the process and links of teaching and learning, which not only greatly improved teachers' lesson preparation efficiency and teaching effect, but it also played a pivotal role in refining teaching methods and applying precision resource delivery (Zheng, 2023). It shows that while education causes social change, it also promotes its own continuous innovation, but talent is the key to cause these changes. With the phenomenal progression of information technology, the demand for individuals possessing innovative spirit and creative capabilities in contemporary society is exceeding any previous eras.

As a new force of scientific and technological innovation, universities should train more qualified and innovative talents for the modernization of the country through innovative personnel training mechanisms and educational methods. Therefore, universities need not only a clear vision, positive policies, sufficient material information resources, a good education environment, but also the real demand of an innovative and entrepreneurial faculty that enriches high quality.

According to the *Implementation Opinions on Deepening the Reform of Innovation and Entrepreneurship Education in Colleges and Universities*, General Office of the State Council of China emphasized that strengthening the teachers' innovation and entrepreneurship educational competence is one of the important tasks to deepen the reform of innovation and entrepreneurship education and promote the development of it in universities. In *Guiding Opinions on Further Supporting University Students' Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, General Office of the State Council of China once again clearly emphasized the

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promotion of teachers' teaching competence in innovation and entrepreneurship education.

Through numerous years of dedicated construction, the scale of teachers specializing in innovative entrepreneurship at Chinese higher education institutions has been consistently increasing, the quality and competence of teachers have been continuously improved, and the institutionalization of teacher performance evaluation has been continuously improved. However, with the continuous advancement of China's innovation-oriented national strategies, the incongruity between the development of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers among universities as well the need for talents of higher education in China is still very prominent.

Statistics from China's Ministry of Education revealed that as of October 2019, there were nearly 28,000 full-time university teachers engaged in innovation and entrepreneurship education field across the whole country. The White Paper titled *Chinese Youth in the New Era* released by the State Council Information Office emphasized that more than 44.3 million Chinese students enrolled among universities in 2021.

In order to provide key support for cultivating useful talents with innovative thinking, innovative consciousness, entrepreneurial spirit and creative competence, it is urgent to speed up the professional competence building of innovation and entrepreneurial teachers in universities, improve their theoretical literacy and practical guidance competence, striving to cultivate a proficient team of highly competent talents.

Literature Review

In 2012, *The Professional Standards for Middle School Teachers* issued by the Ministry of Education of China has made basic provisions on the qualities that middle school teachers should possess as professionals in practice and professional development. The standards included three dimensions: professional concept and moral ethics, professional knowledge and competence. The professional competence consisted of six(6) aspects: instructional planning, instructional implementation, class management and educational activities, assessment of education and teaching, communication and cooperation,

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reflection and development.

In 2013, the notice of *Professional Standards for Teachers in Secondary Vocational Schools (Trial)* made specific provisions on the professional competence of teachers in secondary vocational schools. It included seven (7) specific competence: instructional design, instructional implementation, practical training and internships organization, class management and educational activities, assessment of education and teaching, communication and cooperation, teaching research and professional development. Up to now, there was no professional standard for universities teachers in China. As the level of their professional competence is directly related to their quality of personnel training and the improvement of higher education. Therefore, many researchers concentrated their attention on the research of university teachers' professional competence.

Due to the lack of professional development standards for innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in universities. Studies on the professional competence was not uniform, which were often based on the researchers' own theoretical perspectives and work experience.

Peng (2021), Liu (2019), Guo (2020), Xu (2017), Wang & Long (2020) proposed the composition of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers' professional competence. Su & Zhou (2020), Cui & Wu (2018), Liu & Feng (2017) focused on the teaching competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers, they investigated and analyzed the problems existing and put forward the promotion strategies. Chen (2016) conducted a study on the actuality of young teachers' academic competence in four (4) dimensions, including the level of teaching academic competence, the influencing factors of teaching academic competence, the actual teaching academic investment and the development demand of teaching academic competence. Li et al. (2020) stated that there were many dilemmas in teachers' practice teaching of innovation and entrepreneurship, including lack of original inspiration for innovation, lack practice, and practice training being superficial, based on analyzing the characteristics of practical experience in application-oriented universities. Kaendler et al. (2015) designed a framework for analyzing teachers' collaboration and promoting students' interactions. Xiang et al. (2020) stated that the educational competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers included three (3)

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dimensions: (a) teachers' innovative and entrepreneurial spirit, (b) knowledge, and (c) teaching skills. Liu & Zhang (2015) stated there were many problems in the curriculum development competence of young teachers, including paying more attention to teachers themselves and less attention to students; emphasis the systematization of the subject content, and the lack of the connection between knowledge and related subjects; good mastery of preset content and insufficient utilization of generative resources; skilled in modern technology, but lacking in connection with teaching.

The afore studies have explored teachers' professional competence from different perspectives. However, the professional competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in application-oriented universities has not been given more attention. Therefore, the study attempted to explore the professional competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in application-oriented universities from the perspective of Guangxi.

Method

Descriptive research details variables and their relationships. The objective of it is to delineate a phenomenon and its feature, with emphasis on what happened rather than how or why it happened (Nassaji,2015). The study attempted to investigate the professional competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in application-oriented universities, analyzed the relationship between the competence and their influencing factors, and proposed development support plans. Therefore, the research carried out descriptive research by collecting data through questionnaires.

The participants of the study were 160 innovative and entrepreneurial teachers who were randomly selected in ten (10) application-oriented university in Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China.

To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, the researcher invited five(5) experts who were able to provide comprehensive assessments about the relevance between the contents of the questionnaire and the research objectives. All the validators are Chinese and have established track records of scholarship and competence in their field of study. Moreover, the researcher selected 30 students as the standard population and conducted preliminary tests. After the pilot test, the researchers analyzed the reliability by Cronbach' alpha coefficient.

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From the results, the Cronbach alpha value of the study was 0.978, which exceeded 0.8, thus confirming high quality of the data.

Results and Discussions

This part presents the results and discussions of the statements of the problems, their corresponding answers, and further clarifications.

The Professional Competence of Innovative and Entrepreneurial Teachers

Teacher professional competence is pivotal to enhancing the quality of universities innovation and entrepreneurship education. The work of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers is complex. They should engage in the teaching related courses, and carry out teaching reflection and scientific research according to teaching practice. More important, so as to train students' innovative spirit and potential of future entrepreneurs, teachers must also carry out entrepreneurial training and guidance for students. This series of missions and tasks raise higher requirements for the professional competence of them.

According to Guo (2020), Peng (2021), Liu (2019), Xu (2017), Qi et al. (2017), they have made different generalizations on the dimensions and components of the professional competence of teachers. After fully absorbing and drawing on the achievements of scholars, the researcher summarized the professional competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers into six(6) dimensions, including teaching; scientific research and professional development; entrepreneurial training and guidance; communication and cooperation; student education and management; resource integration.

1. Teaching

Teaching competence is the concentrated embodiment of teachers' professional spirit, which is the essential condition for teachers to satisfy their roles and responsibilities. The level of teachers' teaching competence has an important influence on students' learning effect. Ren (2023) elaborated that teaching competence is a kind of behavior trait that teachers have, obtaining teaching objectives and successfully taking part in teaching activities. Peng (2022) stated that teaching competence mainly included three(3) dimensions: instructional planning, instructional implementation and assessment of teaching.

In the study, on the basis of Peng's opinions, the researcher summarized

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teachers' teaching competence into three(3) perspectives:(a) instructional planning. It is the competence of teachers to design teaching plans and teaching contents reasonably based on fully understanding the training objectives of talents. (b) Instructional implementation. It refers to the enhancement and execution of classroom instruction, usage of teaching methods and tools, guidance during the teaching process, and command of the classroom. (c) Assessment of teaching. It includes teachers' competence to evaluate students and themselves fairly and scientifically during and after teaching implementation. The specific performance of the participants' teaching competence is displayed in the table below.

Table 1 presents the assessment of the teaching competence level of the respondents. It clearly reveals that the grand mean of the dimension "teaching" was 3.72, with an overall verbal description as "competent". This shows that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers have high-level teaching competence. The sample's population standard deviation was 0.70, which implies that there is a certain gap in teachers' teaching competence.

Further analysis of the statement on teaching competence, it shows that the mean of teachers' teaching design competence, such as designing teaching objectives and plans, designing teaching processes and teaching contents, and guiding students to design personalized learning plans, were all above 3.8, with mean of 3.85, 3. 89 and 3. 81 respectively, and verbal interpretation as "competent". This shows that teachers have high-level teaching design competence.

Table 1
Professional Competence in Teaching

Items	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
I can design teaching objectives and teaching plans according to the talent training objectives.	3.85	0.84	Competent

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I can design the teaching process and teaching situation according to the teaching object and teaching goal , and form a reasonable teaching plan.	3.89	0.84	Competent
I can guide and help students to design personalized study plans based on their development endowments.	3.81	0.83	Competent
I can try my best to create a good learning environment and atmosphere, and cultivate students' professional interest and innovative consciousness.	3.94	0.83	Competent
I always integrate international and domestic cutting-edge academic development, the latest research results and practical experience into teaching.	3.48	0.84	Moderately Competent
I often use entrepreneurship competition , creative design, innovative entrepreneurship case analysis and situational teaching methods (such as business games) to carry out teaching.	3.39	0.93	Moderately Competent
I often guide students to solve problems with new ideas in class.	3.81	0.85	Competent
I can apply modern educational technology to implement teaching.	3.90	0.79	Competent
I can use evaluation tools and various evaluation methods to evaluate students' development fairly and guide students to evaluate themselves.	3.81	0.81	Competent
I can self-evaluate the effect of education and teaching , and adjust and improve the education and teaching work in time.	3.88	0.80	Competent
I have participated in teaching competitions at or above the school level and won prizes.	3.12	1.37	Moderately Competent
Grand Mean	3.72	0.70	Competent

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Jin (2015) also pointed out that the teaching competence of teachers at normal colleges were of mid-to-superior level currently.

According to the responses, respondents' performance in classroom teaching organization and implementation competence is somewhat complicated. On the one hand, respondents have good performance in creating a good learning environment and atmosphere, being good at guiding students to solve problems with new ideas and applying modern educational technology to implement teaching, because all the statements with mean above 3.5, with mean of 3.94, 3.81, 3.90, and verbal interpretation as "competent".

On the other hand, the respondents have imperfect performance in integrating advanced international and domestic academic advancements, latest research outcomes, and practical learnings into teaching; using entrepreneurial competition, creative design, innovative and entrepreneurial case analysis and situational teaching methods (such as commercial games) to carry out teaching; and actively participating in teaching competitions and won prizes, because all the statements with mean below 3.5, with mean of 3.48, 3.39, 3.12, and verbal interpretation as "moderately competent".

It shows that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers pay attention to the development of students' innovative thought and have a strong consciousness in shaping a good classroom environment and using new teaching means.

Meanwhile, they should improve their practical application competence and strengthen their own learning in new teaching concepts, new theoretical knowledge and new teaching methods, and their practical application competence needs to be improved.

Based on the responses, the mean of teacher' evaluation for students and themselves were high, with 3.81 and 3.88. It means the level of teachers' teaching evaluation competence is high, which implies that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers are good at teaching reflection and summary, and keep a positive mental state of improvement.

2. Scientific Research and Professional Development

Scientific research competence is the sum of various qualities embodied by scientific researchers in the process of using scientific methods to explore the essence and law of things when they carry out scientific research activities (Xu, 2019). Solid and excellent scientific research competence is the foundation for

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teachers to enrich their knowledge reserves and promote their professional development. In the study, the scientific research competence refers to the teachers' research and self - reflection competence during the process of teaching and practical guidance activities.

Teacher professional development is defined as the process in which teachers continuously improve their professional level, develop continuously and reach professional maturity in their career (Zhang, 2010). Teacher's professional development is the key and core of teacher's quality improvement. Good professional development can not only enhance a steady stream of new knowledge into teachers' scientific research competence and, but also stimulate more research enthusiasm and broaden the horizon of academic research.

The scientific research and professional development competence of the respondents are clearly presented in Table 2. The grand mean was 3.34, with standard deviation of 0.75, and the verbal interpretation as "competent". It indicates that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers have a medium level of scientific research and professional development competence, and there is a certain gap in their competence.

Table 2

Professional Competence in Scientific Research and Professional Development

Items	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
I can explore and study the practical needs and problems in education and teaching.	3.60	0.88	Competent
I have experience of participating in the declaration of teaching research and reform projects at all levels.	3.29	1.21	Moderately Competent
I have presided over teaching reform projects at the provincial level and above.	2.21	1.29	Incompetent
I can formulate my personal professional development plan in combination with the needs of	3.47	0.93	Moderately Competent

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industry enterprises and professional development.			
If there is an opportunity, I hope to improve my education and study full-time.	3.96	1.01	Competent
I can actively collect the latest information about innovation and entrepreneurship in an effective way and internalize it.	3.54	0.94	Competent
Grand Mean	3.34	0.75	Moderately Competent

From the perspective of respondents' scientific research competence, they answered the statement that "I can explore and study the practical needs and problems in education and teaching", got the mean of 3.60, with the verbal interpretation as "competent". It shows that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers have a strong willingness to reflect and summarize their teaching, and carried out scientific exploration and research activities initiatively.

However, the practical results are not perfect. Because the statement of "I have experience of participating in the declaration of teaching research and reform projects at all levels" got a mean of 3.29, with the verbal interpretation as "moderately competent". Moreover, the statement that "I have presided over teaching reform projects at the provincial level and above" got lowest mean of 2.21, with the verbal interpretation as "incompetent". It shows that the teachers' scientific research competence is relatively low, especially for teaching reform.

Chen (2016) pointed out that young teachers' teaching academic competence level was generally good, but teachers' competence to integrate teaching and scientific research was insufficient, and the openness of teaching academic achievements was not high. It is consistent with the conclusion in the research.

About the professional development competence, the respondents are eager to improve their professional knowledge and skills. They have a positive attitude towards improving their education and full-time study, with a mean of 3.96, and the verbal interpretation as "competent". At the same time, they can also actively collect the latest information in an effective way and internalize it

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into their own knowledge. The mean was 3.54, with the verbal interpretation as “competent”.

However, some teachers can't handle the current and long-term relationship with their own professional development. The statement that “I can formulate my personal professional development plan in combination with the needs of industry enterprises and professional development”, got the mean 3.47, with the verbal interpretation as “moderately competent”. In other words, some teachers are not very clear about their future vision and goals.

3. Entrepreneurial Training and Guidance

As an extension of school classroom teaching, entrepreneurship training and service was an essential link to enhance students' innovative and entrepreneurial competence. A qualified entrepreneurial instructor should be a “scholar with entrepreneurs” and a “double-qualified” talent who can teach and do. He knew how to tap entrepreneurial opportunities; how to set up, operate and manage enterprises; and how to prevent and control entrepreneurial risks. He was familiar with entrepreneurial processes, proficient in enterprise management and had entrepreneurial practical competence (Xu, 2017).

Teachers' entrepreneurial training and guidance competence refers to the competence to guide students to carry out innovative experiments, entrepreneurial training and practice with the goal of improving students' comprehensive quality of entrepreneurship, and the orientation of solving entrepreneurial problems. It includes (a) providing students with guidance services for innovation and entrepreneurship competitions or innovative projects; (b) providing students with information consulting services, and entrepreneurship training and diagnosis services; (c) providing students with training and assistance in innovation experiments, simulated entrepreneurial projects or entrepreneurial project incubation; and (d) identifying entrepreneurial opportunities and risks.

It's uncovered in table 3 that the entrepreneurial training and guidance competence obtained a grand mean of 3.08, described verbally as “moderately competent”. It implies that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers in application-oriented universities have moderate level entrepreneurial training and guidance competence. The standard deviation of this dimension was 0.95, which showed that the distribution of data points was relatively scattered. It implies that there is a big gap between teachers' entrepreneurial training and guidance

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competence.

According to the responses, respondents got the best answer in the dimension of providing students to take part in innovation and entrepreneurship competitions or to declare big innovation projects, only with the mean of 3.34, and the verbal interpretation as “moderately competent”.

Table 3
Professional Competence in Entrepreneurial Training and Guidance

Items	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
I have experience in guiding students to participate in innovation and entrepreneurship competitions or to declare big innovation projects.	3.34	1.33	Moderately Competent
I can provide legal and policy consulting services for students' entrepreneurship, and guide students to carry out economic activity analysis.	3.12	1.06	Moderately Competent
I have the competence to identify entrepreneurial opportunities and create opportunities, the competence to identify risks, and can provide students with certain entrepreneurial guidance.	3.13	1.07	Moderately Competent
I can provide targeted training to entrepreneurial students and their teams.	3.17	1.05	Moderately Competent
I often participate in the activities of student associations such as innovation and entrepreneurship associations and entrepreneurship clubs, and carry out practical guidance.	2.99	1.01	Moderately Competent
I can guide students to turn innovative ideas into practical applications, and guide students to carry out innovative experiments.	3.20	1.12	Moderately Competent

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I have experience in guiding students to start business incubation.	2.63	1.23	Moderately Competent
Grand Mean	3.08	0.95	Moderately Competent

Moreover, respondents' competence in these two(2) dimensions also was not ideal, that is, providing students with information consulting services and entrepreneurship training and diagnosis services needed for entrepreneurship, and providing training and help for students in innovative experiments, simulated entrepreneurial projects or the incubation process of entrepreneurial projects. In these two(2) statements, "guide students to turn innovative ideas into practical applications, and to carry out innovative experiments" and "provided students with certain entrepreneurial guidance", with the mean of 3.20 and 3.13. For these two(2) statements, "the teachers' practice of guiding students' club activities" and "business incubation" got the most unsatisfactory answers, with mean below 3.0, 2.99 and 2.63 respectively, and the verbal interpretation as "moderately competent".

Entrepreneurship education is called the "third passport" of education by UNESCO. Gautam & Singh (2015) stated the cultivation of key entrepreneurial competence was not only a matter of acquiring knowledge. As entrepreneurship education was about cultivating the competence to act as an entrepreneur, attitude and behavior may be more important than the knowledge about how to operate the business.

To develop the mentioned entrepreneurial competence, teachers need to teach students entrepreneurial skills through innovative and unconventional teaching methods based on action and practice.

Li, et al. (2020) emphasized that the quality of practical teaching depended largely on teachers' practical teaching competence. Therefore, the cultivation and promotion of university students' entrepreneurial competence largely depended on teachers' own entrepreneurial training and guidance competence.

Regarding the reality of entrepreneurship education in universities, Xu (2017) pointed out that entrepreneurship instructors were obviously "incapable" in entrepreneurship theory and skills. This further confirms the problems revealed in this study.

4. Communication and Cooperation

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Communication was the transmission of information, thoughts and emotions between people (Peng & Wang, 2014). Communication competence lied in whether information can be properly applied to interactive situations. *Ci Hai* defines cooperation as "joint action between individuals or groups through coordination to achieve a certain goal".

Teachers' good communication and cooperation competence is the basic safeguard to promote the information and resources transmitted effectively between teachers, students and peers. It is also the basic condition to promote the ordered development of outreach work between teachers and parents, communities and governments. In the study, the communication and cooperation competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers mainly includes three(3) dimensions:(a)teacher-student communication, (b) peer communication, and (c) outreach communication.

As displayed in table 4, the communication and cooperation competence got a grand mean of 3.90, described verbally as "competent" by the respondents. It implies that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers attach great importance in the establishment and upholding of interpersonal relations, and have good skills and competence in dealing with interpersonal relations activities. The standard deviation of this dimension was 0.78, indicating that there is some gap in teachers' communication and cooperation competence.

The respondents had the best performance in teacher-student communication. In the statements, "take the initiative to understand students and communicate with them equally" and "often encourage students to participate in discussions and express their opinions", got the mean above 4.00, 4.15 and 4.10 respectively, and verbally described as "competent". It shows that teachers fully realize that teaching activities are not unilateral knowledge instillation by teachers, but an interactive process between teachers and students. Lin Liru was a famous educator, who emphasized that teaching was a bilateral activity between teachers and students, not a unilateral teaching by teachers. In teaching, teachers certainly played a leading role, but students' subjective participation was also the key (Hu, 2014). This further illustrated the importance of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers actively approaching and communicating with students, encouraging students to fully participate in the classroom.

Table 4

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Professional Competence in Communication and Cooperation

Items	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
I can take the initiative to understand students and communicate with them equally.	4.15	0.90	Competent
In class , I often encourage students to participate in discussions and express their opinions.	4.10	0.86	Competent
I often cooperate and communicate with colleagues, share teaching experience and resources, and discuss academic issues and the latest trends of employment and entrepreneurship.	3.66	0.97	Competent
I can cooperate and promote the establishment of cooperative and mutual assistance relationship between schools , enterprises and communities , promote school-enterprise cooperation, and provide social services.	3.61	1.00	Competent
When I meet a difficult problem at work , I often discuss it with others to find a solution.	4.00	0.87	Competent
Grand Mean	3.90	0.78	Competent

Respondents also perform well in handling relationships among their peers. The statement, "I often cooperate and communicate with colleagues, share teaching experience and resources, and discuss academic issues and the latest trends of employment and entrepreneurship" got mean of 3.66, with the verbal interpretation as "competent". It implies that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers are willing to actively maintain a good working relationship.

About the two(2) statements, "I can cooperate and promote the establishment of cooperative and mutual assistance relationship between schools, enterprises and communities, promote school-enterprise cooperation, and provide social services" and "when I meet a difficult problem at work, I often

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discuss it with others to find a solution", the mean was 3.61 and 4.00, with the verbal interpretation as "competent". It indicates that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers have a high level in dealing with outreach work.

5. Student Education and Management

Student management was the general term for the school to plan, organize, coordinate and control the learning and activities of students in and out of the school purposefully, planned and organized according to the educational standards stipulated by the educational policy. The education and management competence refers to the competence of teachers to cope with various emergencies in the teaching process and provide necessary career planning guidance and entrepreneurial psychological guidance for students when they instruct the practice innovation and entrepreneurship.

The unique characteristics of college students posed difficulties for the implementation of human resource management within university innovation and entrepreneurship organizations. There existed a potential issue amongst these students, displaying low engagement and low persistence during their practical term in on-campus innovative entrepreneurship platforms (Xie,2020). Therefore, stimulating and developing the student education and management competence of innovation and entrepreneurial teachers to help the students form scientific professional values and healthy professional psychology, is a realistic call to effectively deal with the problems of human resources management and stimulate students' enthusiasm for innovation and entrepreneurship.

As table 5 shown, the student education and management competence of respondents got the grand mean of 4.05, which was described verbally as "competent". It indicates that the students' education and management competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers is at a high level. However, the standard deviation was 0.79, indicating that there is still a certain gap between teachers in this competence.

Table 5
Professional Competence in Student Education and Management

Items	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
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I can provide students with necessary career planning , employment guidance.	4.01	0.87	Competent
I can provide psychological counseling for students in their study and life.	4.09	0.81	Competent
I can deal with emergencies in teaching timely, calmly and appropriately.	4.05	0.84	Competent
Grand Mean	4.05	0.79	Competent

The two (2) statements, "I can provide students with necessary career planning, employment guidance" and "I can provide psychological counseling for students in their study and life" got the mean above 4.0, 4.01 and 4.09 respectively, with the verbal interpretation as "competent". It implies that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers focus on the teaching of students' knowledge and skills, as well as attach great importance to leading the career direction and mental health construction. The statement of " I can deal with emergencies in teaching timely, calmly and appropriately", got the mean of 4.05. It shows that teachers have strong emergency management competence and can deal with all kinds of emergencies in teaching independently.

6. Resource Integration

Curriculum resources are various conditions that are rich in educational value and can be transformed into or serve the school curriculum. Bin (2015) stated that curriculum resources were external and objectifying, which cannot be consciously and directly into the classroom. Teachers were the core elements of curriculum implementation. The educational value of curriculum resources can be demonstrated, only when teachers timely develop and effectively use curriculum resources according to their own knowledge, experience and competence, based on students' actual situation. Therefore, it should be a teacher's competence to integrate various teaching resources.

Based on table 6, the grand mean of the respondents' resource integration competence was 3.65, verbally described as "competent", which shows that respondents have a high competence to integrate resources. It indicates that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers can actively enrich the teaching content with various resources, expand the teaching form, and provide better employment and entrepreneurship opportunities and ways for university student.

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Its overall standard deviation was 0.88, indicating that there is a certain gap in the resource integration competence of innovation and entrepreneurial teachers.

In the study, the competence of resource integration refers to the competence of innovative and entrepreneurial teachers to identify, screen and process resources from different sources, levels and contents, and effectively integrate them in educational practice activities.

Table 6
Professional Competence in Resource Integration

Items	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
I can use alumni resources to create innovative experiments, internships and employment opportunities for students.	3.60	0.96	Competent
I can turn scientific research results into teaching resources and apply them to teaching practice.	3.55	0.98	Competent
I can learn from open education resources, such as massive open online course resources and online video open classes, to carry out learning and auxiliary teaching.	3.79	0.93	Competent
Grand Mean	3.65	0.88	Competent

According to the responses, the statement "I can use alumni resources to create innovative experiments, internships and employment opportunities for students" received a mean of 3.6, with the verbal interpretation as "competent". It shows that innovation and entrepreneurial teachers have a high competence to contact alumni resources and integrate resources. As Fan (2016) explained that actively utilizing alumni resources and organizing students to carry out social practice and internship in alumni enterprises can improve graduates' employability and provide reliable employment channels for university students.

Based on the responses, the statement of "I can turn scientific research results into teaching resources and apply them to teaching practice" got the mean of 3.55, and the verbal description was "competent". It shows that

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innovation and entrepreneurial teachers' transform scientific research results competence is high.

Ye&Liang (2020) stated that as two major functions of universities, teaching was the process of imparting known and mature knowledge, while scientific research was the process of exploring and researching unknown fields, and the two(2) were mutually reinforcing.

Policy Paper on Accelerating the Institution of High-caliber Undergraduate Education to Enhance Talent Cultivation Capability

The Ministry of Education (2018) in the *Opinions on Accelerating the Construction of High-level Undergraduate Education and Comprehensively Improving the Ability to Cultivate Talents* stressed that it was necessary to consolidate the educational function of scientific research, timely transformed the latest achievements in scientific research into education and instructional content so as to support the cultivation of high-quality undergraduate talents.

Liu, et al. (2022) believed that converting the research of scientific achievements into high-quality undergraduate resources in teaching was crucial to promote the quality and talent training. Therefore, teachers with good competence to transform scientific research results helped actively to promote innovative and entrepreneurial teaching to gain better effects.

With the statement "I can learn from open education resources, such as massive open online course resources and online video open classes, to carry out learning and auxiliary teaching" got the mean of 3.79, with the verbal interpretation as "competent". It implies that innovation and entrepreneurial teachers have high level of competence to use open educational resources.

Qiu, et al. (2021) pointed out MOOCs were made a contrast to the traditional teaching mode, which were free from time and space constraints, easy to use, wide coverage, independent learning and other characteristics. They can better solve the bottlenecks faced by entrepreneurship education courses of university students, such as narrow teaching area, weak interaction, weak teachers, and single learning methods. Therefore, it was widely welcomed by students. The openness of MOOCs can improve the level of college teachers (Zhang, 2016).

Zeng (2023) stated that the online video open course, bring into play to optimizing and integrating of the Internet in the distribution of resources. The

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efficiency of students' knowledge acceptance can be promoted and the deficiency of project courses can be made up, if the Internet was creatively applied to educational activities.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis, it is uncovered that innovative and entrepreneurial teachers' professional competence in six(6) dimensions presented unbalanced development. Innovative and entrepreneurial teachers got relatively high score in the four (4) dimensions: student education and management, communication and cooperation, teaching, resource integration, which reflects a high level of competence. It indicates that teachers in application-oriented universities can actively take on the mission and task of imparting knowledge and educate people and exert their own potential to push forward the development of teaching work.

What is worth noting was that teachers' scores were relatively low in the two(2) dimensions: scientific research and professional development, entrepreneurial training and guidance, which reflected the moderate level of competence. The lack of these competence may cause teachers to be unable to achieve the promotion of teaching and research; unable to better achieve their own professional improvement; unable to effectively carry out entrepreneurial practice guidance activities.

Therefore, the teaching administrators should actively be concerned the current situation of teachers' competence and put forward practical and effective action plans to support the development of teachers' professional competence.

Recommendations

The "moderately competent" and "competent" professional competence need to be transformed to "very competent" which is the objective of the action plan.

1. Teachers should strengthen self-learning and actively improve the competence of teaching, scientific research and resource integration. They should actively use the school library, massive open online course, online open classes and other resources and ways to carry out theoretical knowledge learning, constantly broaden their theoretical horizons and enrich their knowledge structure, and update teaching methods and means. Meanwhile, teachers should always pay attention to social and economic trends and enterprise industry trends, and

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update their knowledge structure in real time.

2. They ought to actively participate in various training, and try to enhance the qualification of teachers. Teachers can obtain relevant qualification certificates by participating in national entrepreneurship trainer training and SYB entrepreneurship training, and can further improve their professional quality and competence through pre-job training, course rotation training and backbone training. They ought to also apply for master's and doctoral programs at home or abroad and consciously upgrade their academic qualifications to realize the professional development.

3. They actively take the initiative to establish contact with local enterprises, strive for various opportunities to visit enterprises regularly, or take advantage of the short-term project cooperation with enterprises in winter and summer vacations to continuously enrich the practical experience and improve their own entrepreneurial training and guidance competence.

4. They should actively make use of various experience exchanges and academic lectures held by the school to keep learning and communicating with outstanding teacher representatives and outstanding entrepreneurs, so as to further strengthen communication and cooperation competence.

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